

Farmer Clusters: Working together to address the biodiversity crisis.

Policy recommendations

To promote Farmer Clusters as an effective approach to improve biodiversity, environmental outcomes, and sustainability across farm landscapes the following policies are recommended:

- **Invest in long-term facilitation and support.** Government and rural development policies should embed training, resourcing, and financing for Farmer Cluster facilitators as core elements of agri-environmental programmes. Sustained investment in facilitation is essential to ensure that Farmer Clusters can deliver long-term benefits for biodiversity, agricultural landscape resilience, and rural communities supporting the environmental and climate objectives within CAP 2023-2027.
- **Enhance access to advice, training, and monitoring tools.** Policy should prioritise funding for knowledge exchange platforms, tailored training, and shared monitoring protocols. These tools ensure that farmers have the information, skills, and support needed to implement, assess, and adapt their conservation efforts within their clusters.
- **Voluntary, group-based incentives within AES must be established, maintained and actively supported.** Develop and embed flexible incentives that reward collaborative action and enable collective results within AES, as they play a crucial role in fostering collaboration among farmers and promoting biodiversity-aware practices in landscape scale. Build on successful pilots across Europe to embed group result-based payments and voluntary clustering as core elements of national policy, reinforcing both rural resilience and ecological benefits.

Transformative impact of Farmer Clusters on farmland biodiversity

Biodiversity in agricultural ecosystems has undergone a significant decline, primarily driven by changes in land use. These changes include the expansion of field sizes, the reduction of semi-natural habitats within agricultural landscapes, and the intensification of the farming practises. Such biodiversity loss poses substantial risks to the delivery of key ecosystem services that are essential for sustainable crop production. While the preservation and restoration of seminatural habitats, crop diversification, implementations of long-term crop rotations, and agronomically and environmentally justified use of agrochemicals are the key practices for maintaining and enhancing biodiversity in agricultural landscapes, their impact is often limited to the farm level. Achieving meaningful changes, however, requires coordinated action at the landscape scale.

The Farmer Cluster concept originated from a project by the Game and Wildlife Conservation Trust, which established nature improvement areas through the farmers collaborations, using as bottom-up farmer-lead approach to conservation. Building on this foundation, the Farmer Cluster model was developed as a grassroot approach that enables farmers within the same region to interact, share

expertise, and collectively identify their conservation objectives. Unlike traditional top-down agri-environmental schemes (AES), which often fail to align with farmers local realities, values, and identities, the Farmer Cluster model empowers farmers to the ownership of biodiversity efforts within their landscapes.

Approach and results

The **EU Horizon 2020 project FRAMEwork** explores the potential to replicate the Farmer Cluster model across Europe to enhance farmland biodiversity at a continental scale. Between 2020 and 2021, eleven clusters, regrouping 124 farms, were established in eight countries: the UK, Austria, the Czech Republic, Estonia, France, Italy, Luxembourg, the Netherlands, and Spain, and varied in size, farming system, organisational structure, and the degree of connectivity between farms. Biodiversity-friendly practices introduced by the Farmer Clusters include the introduction of wildflower margins, meadow restoration, hedgerow and tree planting, and the installation of bat and bird boxes. Learning on experiences from the FRAMEwork project, this policy brief explains how Farmer Clusters can play a role in promoting biodiversity, ecosystem services and sustainable farming practices; collaboration and knowledge exchange; and landscape-scale biodiversity monitoring.

In Estonia, the Kanepi Kihlkund Farmer Cluster joined 14 farmers managing over 3000 ha of agricultural land. Their primary goal was to preserve and enhance the status of native species, with a particular focus on wild pollinators. To promote greater heterogeneity and biodiversity in croplands, native wild plant seed mixes were established along the edges of fields. Additional priorities included the conservation of native farmland wild flowers that have been disappearing from the landscape, such as the globeflower (*Trollius europaeus*) and bird's-eye primrose (*Primula farinosa*).

Evidence of impact

By fostering collaboration among farmers within shared landscapes, Farmer Clusters serve as platforms for implementing sustainable practices, spurring innovation, and enhancing ecological resilience.

- **Identity change drives lasting behaviour**

Facilitated Farmer Clusters allow farmers to reimagine their role in biodiversity conservation. Through trust and peer exchange, they transition from isolated efforts to collaborative, nature-friendly practices. This shift in identity—from compliance to stewardship—encourages long-term behavioural change. Interviews show that many farmers embraced terms like “nature-friendly farming” and developed a deeper sense of responsibility, turning sceptics into advocates and embedding conservation values in rural communities (Bohnet et al., 2025).

- **Tangible ecosystem benefits and sustainable practices**

Farmer Clusters can deliver measurable environmental benefits—from improved soil health to increased biodiversity. Localised practices, such as zero tillage and cover cropping in Scotland’s Buchan cluster, enhance soil life and retention. In Austria flower strips and species-rich grasslands restore pollinator habitats and floral diversity. In France and Italy, clusters focused on improving natural pest control and sustainable farming, illustrating how collective action benefits both nature and agriculture. Farmer Cluster concept can be adapted to the local

ecological, and cultural conditions, ensuring the implementation of the practises remain ecologically viable while supporting the agricultural production.

- **Landscape-scale biodiversity monitoring and citizen science**

Monitoring is vital for understanding the effectiveness of conservation measures and guiding result-based payments. FRAMEwork adapted tried and tested protocols used in existing monitoring schemes for use within Farmer Clusters, allowing farmers to assess changes in habitats and species across farms and between holdings. In addition, involving communities in data collection through citizen science methods creates a shared understanding of ecological changes across the landscape, build trust between farmers and the public, and foster a sense of shared purpose. They help farmers and communities alike to take ownership of the evidence base that guides biodiversity conservation, making it more relevant, resilient, and deeply rooted within rural areas.

Policy implications

Successful Farmer Clusters depend on three interlinked pillars: skilled facilitation, access to tailored knowledge and guidance, and well-designed incentives for collaboration. Evidence from the FRAMEwork project across Europe highlights how these elements can work together to drive long-term conservation outcomes.

- **Skilled facilitation is essential**

Facilitators are the linchpins of effective Farmer Clusters. They coordinate meetings, deliver training, monitor progress, and connect farmers with NGOs, researchers, and policymakers. Where facilitation was strong, trust and peer learning flourished; where it was weak, engagement declined. Well-resourced facilitators are vital for building cohesion, sustaining motivation, and ensuring lasting impact (Bohnet et al., 2025). Policy must **prioritise investment in facilitator training and support** to maintain momentum and avoid fragmentation.

- **Access to knowledge, advice, and practical tools**

Farmers need more than goodwill—they need the right information at the right time. Platforms like Recodo.io provide open-access training, biodiversity monitoring protocols, and stakeholder engagement resources that empower both facilitators and farmers. These tools enable the adoption of biodiversity-friendly practices and align local actions with broader conservation goals. Policy should ensure that such platforms are widely accessible, regularly updated, and tailored to local contexts. In Estonia, for example, farmers have emphasized the importance of having materials and guidance available in Estonian to ensure meaningful participation and knowledge uptake across farming community. Although Estonians generally have a strong command of English, they still value access to information in their native language. The development and dissemination of guidance materials in Estonian at both local and national levels is perceived not only as practical necessity but also signals the strategic relevance of the subject.

- **Incentives that support voluntary, collective action**

Incentives are most effective when they respect farmers' autonomy and foster collaboration. FRAMEwork findings show that schemes with voluntary collaboration consistently outperform mandatory Farmer Cluster participation. Clusters saw **higher engagement** when incentives allowed **flexible participation** and supported peer-led initiatives. Collective result-based payments enhanced conservation outcomes and **built peer accountability**. Particularly in high-

risk settings, collective payments improved cooperation by leveraging the potential for collective risk-sharing. Policymakers should design incentive structures that are adaptable, locally relevant, and rooted in shared goals.

Farmer Clusters can serve as a valuable tool to support the objectives of the CAP 2023-2027 and Estonian Agriculture and Fisheries Strategy 2030 (AFS 2030), which places strong emphasis on maintaining a clean environment and preserving biodiversity to ensure the long-term sustainability of the sector.

References / Further Reading

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To learn more about the FRAMEwork eleven Farmer Cluster, see <https://recodo.io/page/farmer-clusters/farmer-cluster-finder>.

About this Policy Brief

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Permalink: <https://zenodo.org/uploads/17176859>

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Project name: FRAMEwork: Farmer clusters for Realising Agrobiodiversity Management across Europe

Project website: www.framework-biodiversity.eu

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Funding

This Project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 862731.